

Simultaneous determination of paracetamol, pseudoephedrine and diphenhydramine in cold medicines using net analyte signal concept

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Abstract : In this work a new modification of the standard addition method called Net Analyte Signal Standard Addition Method (NASSAM) was presented for the simultaneous spectrophotometry analysis of paracetamol, pseudoephedrine and diphenhydramine. In this method, the norm of NAS was calculated and correlated to the concentration of analyte by UV-Vis spectrophotometry technique. In this work, pH 8.0 was selected as an optimum parameter for increasing selectivity and omitting some cationic species. The method can be applied for the determination of analytes in the presence of known interferents. The accuracy of the predictions is not dependent on the shape of the analyte and interferent spectra. NASSAM is a simple and sensitive method with high selectivity and low expenses. The detection limits for paracetamol, diphenhydramine and pseudoephedrine have determined as 0.08, 0.08 and 0.22 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ with linear dynamic range of 0.2–200, 0.2–200 and 0.5–8000 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ respectively. The proposed method has successfully applied to the simultaneous determination of paracetamol, pseudoephedrine and diphenhydramine in cold stop tablets.

Keywords : Paracetamol, pseudoephedrine, diphenhydramine, NASSAM, cough syrup.

Introduction

Cough and cold pharmaceutical preparations are one of the most extended formulations in the world and have got many pharmaceutical forms : syrup, suspension, sachets, capsules and tablets¹. These preparations represent complex formulations containing several active ingredients and a broad spectrum of excipients such as flavoring agents, saccharine or aspartame, acidulates, natural or artificial coloring and flavoring agents, dyes, sweeteners and preservatives^{2,3}. The majority of these ingredients are present as a mixture of basic nitrogenous amino compounds and their separation in pharmaceutical forms is quite complicated due to similarities of their physical and chemical properties⁴.

Paracetamol (PAR) (*N*-(4-hydroxyphenyl)acetamide) (Fig. 1A) is used to treat many conditions such as headache, muscle aches, arthritis, backache, toothaches, colds, and fevers. Acetaminophen is used for the relief of pains associated with many parts of the body. It has analgesic properties comparable to those of aspirin, while its anti-

inflammatory effects are weaker. It is better tolerated than aspirin in patients in whom excessive gastric acid secretion or prolongation of bleeding time may be a concern. Available without a prescription, it has in recent years increasingly become a common household drug. Mechanism and site of analgesic effect of paracetamol is unknown. Setting the center of paracetamol with a direct effect on the hypothalamus and increases heat loss through thermal expansion vessels and sweating, fever is reduced. Paracetamol can relieve pain in mild arthritis but has no effect on the underlying inflammation, redness, and swelling of the joint. It is as effective as the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug ibuprofen in relieving the pain of osteoarthritis of the knee^{5–8}. Pseudoephedrine (PSU) (2-methylamino-1-phenylpropan-1-ol) (Fig. 1B) is an effective sympathomimetic agent for use as a nasal decongestant with peripheral effects similar to epinephrine and central effects similar to, but less intense than, amphetamines. At the recommended oral dosage, it has little or no pressor effect in normotensive adults. The drug pro-

duces fewer adverse effects than ephedrine, specifically, tachycardia, hypertension, and central nervous system stimulation⁸.

Diphenhydramine (DPH) (2-(diphenylmethoxy)-*N,N*-dimethylethanamine) (Fig. 1C), originally used to treat coughs and colds, allergies and nausea. This drug will give the obvious effects of sedation and may produce drowsiness.

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of paracetamol (A), pseudoephedrine (B) and diphenhydramine (C).

The combination of acetaminophen, diphenhydramine, and pseudoephedrine is used to treat runny or stuffy nose, sinus congestion, sneezing, and pain or fever caused by allergies or the common cold⁹.

Several gas chromatographic^{10,11} and high-performance liquid chromatographic (HPLC) methods have been described for determination of pseudoephedrine in plasma¹²⁻¹⁵. The limit of quantitation (LOQ) of HPLC assays ranges between 10 and 50 ng mL⁻¹. Sample preparation was performed by liquid-liquid extraction¹², solid-phase extraction¹³ or column switching^{14,15}. Many methods exist for paracetamol quantification in plasma samples,

including GC¹⁶, GC-MS¹⁷, reversed-phase LC with UV¹⁸⁻²¹, and liquid chromatographic-tandem mass spectrometric (LC-MS-MS)²². Some procedures have been described for the assay of either chlorpheniramine or pseudoephedrine in biological fluids, such as GC²³, LC with radioimmunoassay²⁴, fluorescence²⁵, UV²⁶⁻²⁸, MS^{29,30}, MS-MS detections³¹. Recently, an LC-MS-MS method was also reported to determine simultaneously paracetamol and chlorpheniramine in human plasma, but the extraction recovery of paracetamol was only approximately 20%³². Chen *et al.* have reported an LC-MS-MS method for simultaneous determination of chlorpheniramine and pseudoephedrine in plasma³³. At the same time, none of these methods demonstrate the simultaneous quantification of paracetamol, pseudoephedrine and diphenhydramine in the presence of each other.

The quality control of dosage form preparations of drug requires reliable and quick analytical methods. UV/Vis spectrophotometry is by far the instrumental technique of choice in industrial laboratories, owing mainly to its simplicity and often demanding low cost equipment³⁴. Simultaneous quantitative analysis of pharmaceuticals containing multi-active compounds is difficult to perform by classical spectrophotometric method due to overlapping spectra.

In this work, NASSAM is used for the spectrophotometric determination of paracetamol, pseudoephedrine and diphenhydramine in the multicomponent system. This method combines the advantages of standard addition method with those of net analyte signal concept. The method can be applied for the determination of analyte in the presence of known interferences and the accuracy of the predictions against H-point standard addition method does not depend on the shape of the analyte and interferent spectra.

Theory :

The net analyte signal (NAS) was defined by Lorber³⁵, based on spectroscopic methods, as the part of the spectrum of a mixture that is unique for the analyte of interest, i.e. it is orthogonal to the spectra of the interferences.

The conventional notations have been used throughout the following theoretical discussion. Boldface capital letter is used for a matrix, a boldface lower case for a

column vector and lightface lower case italic for a scalar. The superscript “T” designates the operation of the vector or matrix transposition and the superscript “+” denotes the pseudo-inverse of a non-square matrix. The digitized spectrum is referred to as a spectrum vector or simply as a vector, while a spectrum vector of a pure component is called a component vector.

Consider a synthetic mixture containing PAR, PSU and DPH in concentration of 10 μmol L⁻¹ for each analyte. The simultaneous determination of three analytes by NASSAM requires having spectrum vector of a ternary mixture. The standard concentrations of PAR, PSU and DPH are successively added to the sample solution. The recorded absorbances are measured and expressed by the following equations :

$$A_0 = \epsilon_{\text{PAR}}C_{\text{PAR}}^0 + \epsilon_{\text{PSU}}C_{\text{PSU}}^0 + \epsilon_{\text{DPH}}C_{\text{DPH}}^0 \quad (1)$$

$$A_1 = A_0 + \epsilon_{\text{PAR}}C_{\text{PAR},s_1} + \epsilon_{\text{PSU}}C_{\text{PSU},s_1} + \epsilon_{\text{DPH}}C_{\text{DPH},s_1} \quad (2)$$

$$A_i = A_{i-1} + \epsilon_{\text{PAR}}C_{\text{PAR},s_i} + \epsilon_{\text{PSU}}C_{\text{PSU},s_i} + \epsilon_{\text{DPH}}C_{\text{DPH},s_i} \quad (3)$$

$$A_n = A_{n-1} + \epsilon_{\text{PAR}}C_{\text{PAR},s_n} + \epsilon_{\text{PSU}}C_{\text{PSU},s_n} + \epsilon_{\text{DPH}}C_{\text{DPH},s_n} \quad (3)$$

where A_0 and A_i are the absorbances of the synthetic mixture before and after of standard additions. C_{PAR}^0 , C_{PSU}^0 , C_{DPH}^0 are the initial concentrations of PAR, PSE and DPH in the mixed sample and C_{PAR,s_i} , C_{PSU,s_i} , C_{DPH,s_i} are added standard concentrations of the above components to the sample in the *i*-th step. Also ϵ_{PAR} , ϵ_{PSU} and ϵ_{DPH} are molar absorptivities of paracetamol, pseudoephedrine and diphenhydramine respectively. The NAS vectors for three compounds after each standard addition, $\text{NAS}_{\text{PAR},i}$, $\text{NAS}_{\text{PSU},i}$ and $\text{NAS}_{\text{DPH},i}$ can be calculated by the following equations respectively :

$$\text{NAS}_{\text{PAR},i} = (I - R^+R)A_i \quad (5)$$

$$\text{NAS}_{\text{PSU},i} = (I - S^+S)A_i \quad (6)$$

$$\text{NAS}_{\text{DPH},i} = (I - T^+T)A_i \quad (7)$$

where “*I*” is an identical matrix, “*R*”, “*S*” and “*T*” are the matrixes of absorbances in different concentrations of interferences (Table 1). By definition, it is always possible to split up the spectrum of a sample “ A_i ” into two distinct parts for example : NAS_{PAR} which is orthogonal to the spectra of the interferences (PSU and DPH) and R^+RA_i . The term “ T^+TA_i ” is a part of the spectrum that

is generated by a linear combination of the spectra of interfering agents. Consequently, “ T^+TA_i ” can not be unique for the analyte of interest, because it can also be produced by a mixture of interferences. The other part of vectors “ NAS_{PAR} ” is orthogonal to the spectra of the interferences reflecting the part of the spectrum which is only depending on the analyte “PAR” presents in the mixture. Similar expressions can be used for PSU and DPH. Therefore the orthogonal vectors of PAR, PSU and DPH which known as NAS_{PAR} , NAS_{PSU} and NAS_{DPH} can be used for quantification of the analytes PAR, PSU and DPH respectively. Fig. 2 shows the geometrical vector presentations of analyte, interferent, sample, R^+RA_i and NAS_{PAR} . The shape of “ NAS_{PAR} ” vector only depends on the presence of interferences in the mixture, not on their specific concentrations.

In binary and/or ternary mixtures when the interferences are known, the NAS vector can be calculated for the each analyte separately. Norm of the NAS vector can be used to construct a univariate calibration model.

Experimental

To demonstrate the analytical applicability of the proposed method for the analysis of ternary mixtures, three pure spectra of PAR, PSU and DPH were recorded separately. As it has shown in Fig. 3, the spectra are too overlapped in the range of 220–320 nm. Fig. 4 shows successive standard addition of three analytes (PAR, PSU and DPH) at the same mole ratio into a ternary mixture. NAS vectors for components were calculated simultaneously based on eqs. (5–7) and demonstrated in Figs. 5A, B and C respectively. As it has shown in Fig. 6, norms of NAS vectors for each analytes are proportional to the standard added concentrations that can be used to calculate the simultaneous concentrations of each analyte.

Chemicals and solvents :

All experiments were performed with analytical grade chemicals and solvents. Stock solutions with 1.0×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ of paracetamol, pseudoephedrine hydrochloride and diphenhydramine (Amin Pharmaceutical Co., Tehran, Iran) were prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount in deionized water and stored at 4 °C in glass flasks. Working solutions were daily prepared by suitable dilution. A phosphate buffer solution (pH 8.0, 0.01 M) was employed for pH adjustment.

Fig. 2. Representation of vector space for analyte (PAR) and other analytes (PSU and DPH) in two dimensional space. The $(NAS)_{PAR}$ vector is different from PAR vector in direction and length.

junction glass electrode used to determine pH of the solutions.

Preparation of real samples :

To assay cold medicine tablets containing paracetamol (500 mg), pseudoephedrine hydrochloride (30 mg) and diphenhydramine (25 mg), five tablets were powdered homogeneously and then 0.010 g of the powder transferred into a 100-mL measuring flask and after dissolving, diluted to the mark by doubly distilled water.

Recommended procedure :

An aliquot of a solution containing PAR, DPH and/or PSU and 1.0 ml Britton-Robinson buffer solution (pH 8.0) added into different volumetric flask (25.0 ml) and made up to the mark with deionized water after successive standard additions of three components (PAR, DPH and PSU) at the same mole ratios. The spectrum of the solution for each volumetric flask recorded in the wavelength range of 220–320 nm and saved as text files. For

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of $20.0 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ paracetamol, $20.0 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ diphenhydramine and $100.0 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ pseudoephedrine at pH 8.0.

Instrumentation and software :

Absorption measurements were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer (Lambda 25) spectrophotometer, using 1.0 cm quartz cells. All spectra were saved in ASCII format and transferred to a PC computer for subsequent manipulation. The data were handled using MATLAB software (R2008a) to calculate the norm of NAS vectors.

A pH-meter (Metrohm, Model 827) with a double

calculating the norm of NAS for each analyte, the matrices of R, S and T designed in the concentration ranges of 0.2–60, 0.2–100 and 0.5–4000 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for paracetamol, diphenhydramine and pseudoephedrine at the wavelength region of 220–320 nm. Then the saved files corresponding to each standard addition transferred to Matlab program for calculating the norms of PAR, DPH and PSU simultaneously [eqs. (5–7)]. In the end,

Fig. 4. The zero order spectra of PAR, PSU and DPH after successive standard additions of free components at the same mole ratios in the concentration range of 10–70 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ for spectra 1–8. The initial solution contains a mixture of paracetamol (50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$), pseudoephedrine (10 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and diphenhydramine (50 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$).

the concentration of each component calculated by extrapolation of the standard addition plots.

Results and discussion

The UV-Vis spectra of PAR, DPH and PSU have shown in Fig. 3 in B-R buffer (pH 8.0). The maximum wavelengths of three compounds are close to each other and their spectra overlapped. Therefore, determination of PAR, DPH and PSU in the presence of each other is impossible by classical spectrophotometry. As an alternative, we used NASSAM as a powerful chemometrics method to solve matrix effect and interferent errors in the analysis of paracetamol, diphenhydramine hydrochloride and pseudoephedrine simultaneously.

Effect of pH :

In order to optimize the procedure for the simultaneous determination of paracetamol, diphenhydramine and pseudoephedrine, the effect of pH on the sensitivity and overlapping of the absorbances studied individually. As it has shown in Fig. 7A, pH is not an effective parameter on the sensitivities of PAR, DPH and PSU. The overlapping between three spectra increased at $\text{pH} > 9.0$ because of the red shifting of paracetamol spectrum in alkali media. Therefore, pH of 8.0 was selected as an optimum pH to obtain higher selectivity.

Reproducibility and limit of detection :

The reproducibility of the proposed method has been investigated. The inter-day precision was investigated by measuring the concentration of ternary synthetic mixtures containing paracetamol, diphenhydramine and pseudoephedrine by NASSAM for 3 times for the different concentrations of the components taken separately (Table 1) and the relative standard deviation was found in the range of 0.58–4.80%. Thus, it demonstrated the good reproducibility of the proposed method.

The limit of detections for paracetamol, diphenhydramine and pseudoephedrine were calculated base on the $\text{LOD} = 3S_C^{36}$, where S_C is the standard deviation of several ($n = 5$) replicated measurement of zero concentration of the analyte with NASSAM. The corresponding values obtained for PAR, DPH and PSU were calculated as 0.324, 0.085 and 0.224 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ respectively.

Analytical applications :

Synthetic ternary samples :

For investigation on the applicability of the proposed method in the simultaneous determination of paracetamol, diphenhydramine and pseudoephedrine, the proposed method applied on the analysis of components by the proposed method (Table 2).

Fig. 5. NAS curves for (A) paracetamol, (B) diphenhydramine and (C) pseudoephedrine. All of the conditions are as Fig. 4.

Fig. 6. Standard addition plots for components PAR, PSU and DPH using norm of the vectors as signals. All of the conditions are as Fig. 4.

Fig. 7. (A) Effect of pH on the maximum absorption spectra of paracetamol, pseudoephedrine and diphenhydramine. (B) Effect of pH on the λ_{max} of paracetamol, pseudoephedrine and diphenhydramine. Conditions : $30.0 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ paracetamol, $20.0 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ diphenhydramine and $300.0 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ pseudoephedrine.

Table 1. Relative standard deviation of PAR, PSU and DPH after successive determination by the proposed method

Mixture	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			RSD (%)		
	PAR	PSU	DPH	PAR	PSU	DPH	PAR	PSU	DPH
1	50.0	50.0	50.0	51.15	50.00	50.00			
2	50.0	50.0	50.0	51.07	50.00	49.23	0.31	1.95	0.89
3	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.84	48.33	50.00			
4	120.0	5.0	3.0	119.84	4.70	2.84			
5	120.0	5.0	3.0	119.61	4.91	2.84	0.58	3.42	4.80
6	120.0	5.0	3.0	120.92	5.03	2.61			

Table 2. Determination of PAR, PSU and DPH in some ternary mixtures

Mixture	Added ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Found ($\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$)			Relative error (%)		
	PAR	PSU	DPH	PAR	PSU	DPH	PAR	PSU	DPH
1	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.07	10.00	10.69	0.70	0.00	6.90
2	10.0	50.0	10.0	10.71	50.00	10.00	7.10	0.00	0.00
3	10.0	100.0	50.0	10.35	100.00	51.84	3.50	0.00	3.68
4	20.0	150.0	6.0	19.78	146.66	5.61	-1.10	-2.22	-6.50
5	15.0	25.0	100.0	15.42	25.00	101.61	2.80	0.00	1.61
6	80.0	20.0	80.0	77.61	20.00	80.92	2.90	0.00	1.15
7	60.0	80.0	40.0	56.64	78.33	41.91	-5.60	-2.08	4.80
8	60.0	20.0	60.0	56.42	20.00	61.91	-5.90	0.00	3.18
9	30.0	60.0	30.0	28.23	55.00	28.71	-5.90	-8.30	-4.30
10	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.83	52.00	45.84	1.66	4.00	-8.30

Table 3. Results of the replicate measurements for determination of PAR, PSU and DPH in some pharmaceutical formulations, expressed as $\bar{X} \pm (tS.D.)/N$, for $N=3$ measurements and $t^{95\%, (N-1=2)} = 2.92$

Sample ^a	Added (mg)			Found (mg)			Recovery (%)		
	PAR	PSU	DPH	PAR	PSU	DPH	PAR	PSU	DPH
Cold stop	-	-	-	496.38 \pm 3.20	33.33 \pm 0.10	25.19 \pm 0.15	99.27	111.0	100.77
Tablet	12.30	8.80	9.50	508.19 \pm 3.20	41.37 \pm 0.23	34.40 \pm 0.25	96.06	91.40	96.94
	21.07	17.60	19.00	516.64 \pm 1.30	51.49 \pm 4.10	43.37 \pm 0.60	96.15	103.18	95.68
Coldax	-	-	-	497.91 \pm 0.50	33.33 \pm 0.54	24.69 \pm 0.90	99.58	111.00	99.86
Tablet	10.00	8.80	9.50	507.58 \pm 0.90	41.37 \pm 0.58	35.24 \pm 1.90	96.70	91.36	105.78
	24.82	18.00	20.00	523.09 \pm 3.70	52.46 \pm 0.89	45.29 \pm 0.90	103.56	106.05	103.00

^aTablet Cold stop and Coldax contains paracetamol (500 mg), pseudoephedrine (30 mg) and diphenhydramine (25 mg) in each tablet.

Pharmaceutical formulations :

The proposed method was applied to the determination of commercial cold stop formulations viz. Cold stop tablets (Loghman Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Tehran) and Coldax (Abidi Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Tehran). The tablets were weighed and finely pulverized. The appropriate amount of this powder was dissolved in double distilled water. The content of pharmaceutical components in the electrochemical cell was diluted to get the concentration in the working range and then UV-Vis spectra were re-

corded. The concentrations of paracetamol, diphenhydramine and pseudoephedrine in the pharmaceutical formulations were determined with the help of NASSAM. Table 3 shows that the content values determined by the proposed method for all the commercial samples are very close to the claimed amount. The analysis of the obtained responses allowed concluding that the drug excipients do not significantly interfere with the proposed method.

Conclusion

The present paper described a highly convenient, rapid

and accurate method for the separation and quantification of paracetamol, diphenhydramine and pseudoephedrine by NASSAM in cold stop medicines for the first time. In addition by using the chemometrics approach, the quantitation of components with highly overlapping spectra was applicable in a short time. Therefore, the economical method can be applied to the quality control of some cold medicines.

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